

Environmental friendly management of acid sulphate soils

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ABSTRACT

Acid sulfate soil (ASS) is the name given to soils and sediments containing iron sulfide minerals, the most common being pyrite. Pyrite is chemically inert in undisturbed and submerged by groundwater. However, when the groundwater level below the sulphidic material layer, pyrite may oxidized to form sulphuric acid. Reclamation of acid sulfate soil for agriculture is often unsuccessful because of mismanagement and treating ASS such as mineral soil in upland. This paper describes an environmental friendly management approach to manage ASS for agriculture in Indonesia. Actually ASS can be successfully managed. Management practices for agriculture require integrated approach such as knowledge of physical, chemical and biological properties of soil, hydrological aspect and climate. It is essential to establish a standar operational procedure or to determine the most appropriate action in managing ASS for agriculture. There are some management options to treat acid sulfate soils, especially for agriculture such as minimization of soil disturbance, water management, neutralization, and bioremediation, etc. Selection of an appropriate management option will depend on soil characteristics, land hydrological condition and the environmental sensitivity of the site.

Key words : *Acid sulphate soils, pyrite, and water management.*

INTRODUCTION

Acid sulfate soils (ASS) are soil type which contains sulfuric acid or in which sulfuric acid may be produced, is being produced, or has been produced in amounts that have a lasting effect on main soil characteristics (Pons 1973). This general definition includes potential and actual sulfate soils (Fanning 2002). Actual ASS are soils that contain sulfuric acid and also sulfidic material at shallow depths (< 50 cm). Whereas soils are called potential acid sulfate soils as they have potential to produce sulfuric acid when disturbed or exposed to air. Some of the more common environments that contain ASS such as coastal and estuarine areas, mangrove swamps, and inland lakes (Fitzpatrick and Shand 2008).

Acid sulfate soils are formed through oxidation of sulfide minerals in soils. Pyrite is most commonly iron sulfide minerals in the natural environment.

Pyrite is formed in anaerobic or highly reductive condition. Iron sulfide minerals contain sulfide and reactive iron (Fe). The conditions for reduction of sulfate to sulfide include (i) sulfate rich water (e.g. sea water), (ii) sulfate reducing bacteria (e.g. *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans*), (iii) source of organic C, and (iv) an anoxic environment (Fanning *et al.* 2002). The process through which sulfide minerals are formed in nature is termed as *Sulfidization*. The exposure of pyrite in air will oxidate these minerals, and a subsequent release of sulfuric acid. When sulfuric acid is released from the soil, it can in turn release iron, aluminium, and other heavy metals into the soil and associated water body. After mobilization, the acid and metals can create adverse impacts on the environment such as killing vegetation, killing fish and other aquatic organisms, degrading concrete and steel structures, seeping into and acidifying soil, groundwater and water bodies (Dent, 1986).

There are 10 M ha of ASS that are found in the Tropic, and about 6.7 M are located in Indonesia (Andriessse and Meensvoort 2006; Noor 2004). Utilization of ASS as agricultural land is known as land reclamation activity. Reclamation activities of acid sulfate soil for agriculture are in land clearing, land arrangement and made a water management systems. These activities are aimed to improve land function, especially land productivity. Land arrangement in the terms of agriculture is intended to achieve a proportional area between rice plantations area and other crops, in addition land arrangement lead more easier in the management of agriculture in terms of various aspects in an integrated manner. The water management system is designed to meet the water needs and create optimum environmental conditions for plant growth both in rainy or dry seasons. Anda and Siswanto (2002) stated that after reclamation, pyrite concentration in 80 to 140 cm-depth soil surface was lower than before reclamation (Figure 1). Pyrite is stable in reductive condition, land reclamation (canal construction) lead pyrite oxidation and causing less pyrite to remain.

Figure 1. The changes of pyrite content of ASS due to land reclamation (Anda and Siswanto, 2002).

On the other hand, land reclamation effort can potentially have a negative impact on the environment, mainly in short term. Land reclamation leads the changes in soil chemical properties that have adverse impact on plants, animals and environment. These condition is related with the potential for acidity and metals toxicity and other toxic potential elements such as CO₂, and SO₄²⁻ which released to the soil, groundwater and water bodies. Das and Das (2012) stated in some areas of Australia, acid sulfate soils that drained 100 years ago are still releasing acid specifically, if the soils are drained or exposed to air by a lowering of the water table, pyrite react with oxygen to form sulphuric acid. Anda and Siswanto (2002) reported pH value after reclamation was lower than before reclamation, but conversely exchangeable Al concentration after reclamation was higher than before reclamation (Figure 2). This condition is related with dillution of proton which accumulated and cocentrated latter. The protons are generated when the groundwater table was below the sulphidic material layer. In dry conditions, evapotranspiration from the groundwater can be lower than water table further, causing pyrite exposed to oxidizing conditions. When the groundwater is recharged by rainfall, the proton can be transported into the soil, groundwater and water bodies (Indraratna et al. 2001). When soil is becomes very acidic, then iron, aluminium, and other heavy metals may release into the soil soilution and water body.

Figure 3. The changes of soil pH and exchangeable Al of ASS due to land reclamation (Anda and Siswanto, 2002).

MANAGEMENT OF ACID SULPHATE SOILS

The presence adverse effect of land reclamation lead to the conclusion that the environmental friendly management strategy of ASS reclamation should avoid pyrite oxidation. In order to reduce pyrite oxidation, the availability of oxygen must be reduced. Therefore, a potential method in reducing oxygen transport to the pyritic layer is maintenance of high groundwater levels above the elevation of pyritic layer.

Various stage of acid sulfate soil reclamation such as land clearing, canal construction, and risebeds construction through excavating or otherwise removing soil or sediment, lowering of groundwater levels or filling or surcharging of low-lying land causes disturbance of acid sulphate soil. Selection of priority management options will depend on the nature and location of the ASS materials, and their position in the landscape. Further characterizing ASS landscapes are so important. Considering the fragile nature of ASS and to reduce the possibility of land degradation and environmental or soil quality, there are some management strategies used to minimize this possibility and its effects. The general approaches for reclamation are suggested as follows (Fitzpatrick et al. 2008; Das and Das 2015):

1. Avoidance

Avoidance is the most preferred management strategy for environmental friendly management of ASS. Acid sulfate soils are inert when left in waterlogged, undisturbed conditions.

2. Minimise disturbance or drainage of ASS

If acid sulfate soils cannot be avoided for crop production, select an alternative non-sulphidic soils is the best option for agriculture development, rather than undertake remediation. If an alternative site is not feasible, their disturbance should be minimized. design works to minimize the need for excavation or disturbance of sulphidic materials, by undertaking shallow excavations for drainage measures and avoiding lowering groundwater depth that may result in exposure of soils.

3. Water management (re-flooding, seawater re-flooding, and intermittent drainage)

In order to reduce pyriteoxidation, the availability of oxygen must bereduced. Van Breemen (1993) stated pyrite oxidation can be curtailed efficiently only by waterlogging. The diffusion of oxygen through water is about105 times slower than through air. Therefore, a potentialmethod of reducing oxygen transport to the pyriticlayer is to maintain high groundwater levels, for examplethrough the use of weirs (Blunden & Indraratna, 2000).

Re-flooding: Land clearing and canal contruction leadlowering groundwater level that may result in exposure of sulphidic materials, then oxidation products of these materialmay export to surrounding environment.The objective of re-flooding is to neutralise acidity and reduce the pyrite oxidation rate. Re-flooding relies on establishing reductive conditions for Fe, Mn, S and N. The reduction of these elements is relate with increasing of soil pH commonly observed in acid soils after water logging. Re-flooding is a water table height-management tool to prevent the oxidation of sulphidic material.

Seawater re-flooding: Re-flooding soil with seawater may trap the existing acid leachate and force it deeper into the soil profile, limiting the export of oxidation products such as hidrogen and aluminium.

Flooding and Intermittent drainage: Soils may be flooded (anaerobic) or buried in water to maintain a saturated state. This solution almost limits the use ofthe area to rice growing. Rice grown under intermittent drainage had better performance and prouction.

Figure 3. Changes in water pH due to improvements water management system (Source: Johnston *et al.*, 2009)

4. Neutralisation
 Provide an agent to neutralise acid as it is produced, this would involve mixing lime, or other neutralising agent to soil. Liming is the most preferred and most important way to reclaim and remediate acid sulphate soil. Lime has an alkaline pH and buffers any oxidation produced whilst raising the soil pH to acceptable levels. Proper mixing the appropriate amount and type of lime into disturbed ASS will neutralise oxidation produced.
5. Hasten oxidation then collecting and treatment of acidic leachate
 Spreading certain materials on ASS mainly in sulphidic layer to activate rapid oxidation. Rainfall or tidal water leaches the acid and this leachate is collected and treated (e.g. by liming and organic matter application).
6. Organic matter application
 Organic matter application to the ASS prevent soil acidification. Decomposition of OM by aerobic bacteria results in oxygen depletion, which then favors metabolic conversion of sulfates to sulfides by anaerobic bacteria. This fact have important implications for the broad scale management of ASS.
7. Bioremediation
 Bioremediation lead water and soil chemical properties changes, and in sediment that may accumulate. Bioremediation technology would be a

natural process and cost-effective if *in-situ* microbial generation of acid-neutralising capacity is significant.

8. Growing of suitable crops

In all environment condition, growing of suitable crops is the most recommended environmental friendly management for agricultural development. Rice is the most preferable crop which is highly acid tolerant. Some rice varieties have high tolerance for soil acidity and iron toxicity that occurs on ASS.

9. Planning and development controls

In the term sustainable agriculture concept. Acid sulphate soil reclamation should be account carefully. Proper planning and development controls for ASS is needed. Acid sulphate soil reclamation that conducted without proper planning and development controls may had serious damage on environment. Practically, reclamation of ASS should be comply a standard guidelines.

Proper management and planning can reduce the damage of ASS, improving soil health and sustaining agriculture practice. Indraratna *et al.* (2005) reported that the modified floodgates were successful in buffering the drain water pH before discharging the drain water into adjacent waterways. Manipulation of the ground water table through floodgate modification and complete inundation of acid-producing materials has been successful in decreasing the pyrite oxidation.

Figure 4. Average groundwater elevation (a) before and (b) after *tabat* (weir) installation, with the maximum and minimum groundwater elevation dashed (Indraratna *et al.*, 2005).

CONCLUSIONS

Acid sulfate soil (ASS) is fragile soils. Reclamation of ASS causes environmental damage, this condition is related with mismanagement of ASS. Actually ASS can be successfully managed, management practices requires integrated approach such as knowledge of physical, chemical and biological properties of soil, hydrological aspect and climate. It is essential to establish a standar operational procedure or to determine the most appropriate action in manage ASS for agiculture. There are some management options to treat acid sulfate soils, especially for agriculture such as avoidance, minimize disturbance or drainage of ASS, water management (re-flooding, seawater re-flooding, and intermittent drainage), neutralization, hasten oxidation then collecting and treatment of acidic leachate, organic matter application, bioremediation, growing of suitable crops, planning and development controls.

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